

APPLYING RECIPROCAL TEACHING APPROACHES FOR DEVELOPING STUDENTS' READING COMPREHENSION SKILLS

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ABSTRACT

Reading is undoubtedly a core skill for students learning a second language. Although reading tasks are more commonly used than other language skills in English classrooms, students' receptive skill outcomes remain low. The reason is associated with the lack of effective reading strategies to enhance comprehensive understanding in reading classes. This study aimed to investigate the effect of Reciprocal Teaching Method (RTM) on the development of EFL learners' reading comprehension skills. RTM incorporates four key strategies: predicting, clarifying, question generating, and summarizing. Beyond supporting students in understanding reading texts, the method also offers opportunities for learners to monitor their own learning and thinking processes. Furthermore, RTM fosters the development of metacognitive skills, leading to improved critical thinking abilities. The participants of the study were 36 university students majoring in Finance and Banking. The findings revealed that RTM leads to better performance, deeper understanding, and stronger long-term learning compared to traditional teaching methods. Specifically, the control group shows a modest gain of about 4.6 percentage points from pre-test to post-test. But the experimental group shows a much larger gain - almost 9 percentage gaps. This demonstrates that the Reciprocal Teaching Method was noticeably more effective in improving students' reading comprehension skills.

Keywords: reciprocal teaching, EFL learners, improving reading comprehension, metacognitive skills, reading strategies, experimental training.

INTRODUCTION

Reading is perceived in various ways as considered as a receptive skill for students' growth in many aspects of their individual life. It is deemed the most crucial activity, serving not only as a source of information and enjoyable experience, but also as a beneficial method for enhancing learners' understanding of language and extending their knowledge, literature and culture to contribute in every aspect of life (Prastyo, 2017). Qurrotul A'yun (Yunus, 2017) claimed that reading is the message receiving activity to understand the content of a text and construct meaning which involves the interaction between text and the reader. According to Mohammad Reza Ahmadi and Abbas Pourhossein Gilakjani (Gilakjani, 2012), reading is a cognitive process that consists of a reader, a text, and the interaction between the reader and the text. Based on the above definitions, reading comprehension can be defined as the mental process of interaction between writer and the reader. In other words, it is explained that the writer encodes a message while the reader decodes the meaning from the text (Rojabi, Exploring reciprocal teaching method on EFL learners' reading comprehension, 2021). As reading comprehension is a mental and constructive process, it involves mental operations through both cognitive and metacognitive strategies that learners can use when they read. Cognitive strategies are used for summarizing, giving reasons, predicting, taking notes on the main points, using prior knowledge, and guessing meaning from the context. Metacognitive strategies allow readers to control their planning, evaluating, and regulating skills by determining the reading task, evaluating the predictions, focusing on important information, checking the effectiveness of guessing meaning, re-reading relevant information, and checking the effectiveness of achieving the whole reading task (Gilakjani, 2012).

Unfortunately, some students confronted with reading difficulties to gain the text's comprehensive

meaning. Under the observation in the reading class, some students engaged passive and unmotivated with limited understanding. One of the reasons for this situation is that the conventional reading method, commonly known as the grammar-translation method, is typically applied in the Mongolian context. Students read particular English passages, translate them into Mongolian language and answering some comprehensive questions. The conventional methods have less effects on students' reading comprehension and motivation to read. That's why, the problem arises from the lack of effective strategies for applying logical and systematic reading techniques that can enhance comprehensive understanding in reading classes. The improper instruction for reading activities are affected to create an inappropriate interaction and less enjoyable atmosphere between teacher and students. Due to the above concern, it is hoped that a specific reading strategies like reciprocal teaching method (RTM), as it is a cooperative learning practice, can be a solution to overcome the learners' challenges in reading comprehension at tertiary level. Reciprocal teaching is originally developed by Palincsar and Brown to improve students' reading comprehension. The method is step by step procedure and emphasize in the following four strategies: predicting, clarifying, questioning and summarizing to enhance reading comprehension (Oczkus, 2018). Theoretically, this method is considered suitable for developing reading comprehension, as it involves several steps through which students activate their prior knowledge, relate it to the reading topic, and enhance understanding through clarification and summarization.

Research questions: The following questions were elaborated below under the research topic.

1. Is there any significant effect of reciprocal teaching method on improving the students' reading comprehension?

2. Is there any significant effect of meta-cognition strategy for applying reciprocal teaching method in the comprehensive reading class?

Research purpose and objectives: This study aimed to investigate the effect of Reciprocal Teaching Method (RTM) on the development of EFL learners' reading comprehension skills at Mandakh University, Mongolia. The study attempted to achieve the following objectives:

1. To compare the effectiveness of the reciprocal teaching approach on students' reading comprehension between experimental and control groups

2. To investigate effectiveness of meta-cognition strategy for applying reciprocal teaching approach between experimental and control groups of comprehensive reading class

LITERATURE REVIEW

Many academics have investigated the efficiency of reciprocal teaching in the university setting (Wimonphon Rawengwan, 2020). The Reciprocal Teaching Model (RTM) enhances reading comprehension through four strategies: predicting, clarifying, questioning, and summarizing. Predicting links prior knowledge to new information, while clarifying helps resolve confusion and monitor understanding. Questioning guides readers to identify main ideas and key details, and summarizing condenses information and connects ideas across paragraphs. Together, these strategies encourage active engagement with the text and improve overall comprehension (Alsarireh, 2016).

In the EFL setting, a researcher I-Chia Chou explored the use of reciprocal teaching with Taiwanese university students enrolled in English Medium Instruction (EMI) courses (Chou, 2016). The results revealed a substantial difference between the test scores before and after the reciprocal teaching intervention. The researcher proposed that the reciprocal teaching style might help Taiwanese students learn academic texts and prepare the EFL teacher for future studies in other EMI courses (Chou, 2016). Similarly, Alsarireh and Hamid evaluated the influence of applying reciprocal teaching method, or RTM, on first-year university students in Jordan through RTM successes in reading competence, concentrating on students' gender (Ku Mohd Nabil Ku Hamid, 2016).

Studies across different contexts found that students using RTM achieved higher scores, developed better strategies, and showed more positive attitudes toward learning (Peter E. Doolittle, 2006). A systematic review made by Ting Pick Dew and others aimed to identify, evaluate and synthesize the evidence regarding the use of reciprocal teaching as a reading intervention for English as a Second Language (ESL) learners. Additionally, it investigated the specific features that contribute to the effectiveness of reciprocal teaching in ESL reading comprehension classrooms (Ting Pick Dew, 2021). As cited by Ting Pick Dew, a significant meta-analytical research conducted by Rosenshine and Meister (1994) supported Palincsar and Brown's (1984) concept of reciprocal teaching as a form of explicit instruction that promotes metacognition throughout the meaning-making process. This claim was later reinforced by McAllum (2014), who described reciproc-

cal teaching as a blend of reading strategies that includes the explicit instruction of metacognitive strategies and a dialogical process that fosters understanding and comprehension, aligning with the shift in reading paradigms (Carter, 1997) (Ting Pick Dew, 2021).

In essence, reciprocal teaching treats reading as a joint endeavor, where the comprehension process involves collaborative instructional strategies that allow small groups of students to learn and apply four reading strategies through guided support. According to the literature reviews, most researches have shown that EFL students often perform poorly in reading comprehension. This is mainly due to three factors, firstly, limited knowledge of reading strategies, secondly, ineffective teaching practices that focus only on silent reading and answering questions without enough time or skill-building, and thirdly, some learners' reluctance or lack of motivation to engage in higher-level reading tasks. Research consistently shows that the RTM enhances reading comprehension more effectively than traditional or translation methods.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research design: The study was employed experimental design with the examination of the effect on reciprocal teaching method as independent variable, and students' reading comprehension as dependent variable. The researcher were as active agents rather than a passive observer.

Quasi-experimental design was applied with pre-test and post-test to achieve the research purpose. The pre-test aim was to check the level of reading comprehension of two groups. The post-test aim was to compare the score of the two groups to evaluate which group gain better score and whether the score is significantly different or not.

Hypothesis 1: RTM affects students to improve their reading comprehension.

Hypothesis 2: Meta-cognition strategy affects students to acquire RTM to monitor their reading comprehension.

Population and sampling: The population consisted of 36 EFL students at Mandakh University, who are majored in Finance and Banking in the academic years 2024-2025 and 202-2026. The participants were assigned to experimental and control groups based on existing class condition rather than randomly. Thus, the experimental group (Group 1) with 20 students were taught by using the RTM. Meanwhile, the control group (Group 2) with 16 students were taught by using the conventional method. To fulfill the research validity requirements, both groups were taught in the same courses and during the same time period. The research administrators informed all participants about the purpose of the study, the data collection process conducted before starting the research implementation, and provided feedback after the experiment. However, the students were not informed about the group to which they had been assigned.

Research Instruments: This study included the following instruments according to the target objectives.

- Reading comprehension placement test: the Cambridge Placement Test (English, 2025) with 25

items was used to find the students' English proficiency level.

- Reading comprehension pre and post tests were taken to compare reading comprehension skills before and after experiment (Teens, 2025).
- Semi-structured interview was undertaken to provide the research reliability and validity.

FINDINGS

This study aimed to investigate the effectiveness of the Reciprocal Teaching Method (RTM) in enhancing students' reading comprehension skills. The participants were junior students from Mandakh university in the frame of Quasi-experimental design. According to the principal of the quasi-experimental design, the participants were assigned into two groups. The experimental group consisted of 20 EFL learners who were instructed using the reciprocal teaching method, while the control group, with 16 EFL learners, received instruction through traditional teaching methods. English proficiency level of the participants was between B1

and B2 level (CEFR), as intermediate that set through a Cambridge General English Placement test with 25 items (English, 2025) before starting the experiment.

Before starting the experiment two groups took pre-test to evaluate the reading comprehension of the participants with B1-level reading texts and post-test was administered after actions to know the learners' improvement on reading comprehension with a standardized test.

During reading, research data were gathered through classroom observation, RTM evaluation worksheets aligned with the four RTM strategies. The worksheets guided students through predicting, clarifying, questioning, and summarizing at each step of the reading process, ensuring consistency and structure. This tool helped us measure how effective the method was and how students experienced the strategies during reading.

A standardized reciprocal teaching rubric, accessible online, was employed for the evaluation.

Table 1

Reciprocal teaching rubric for informative reading

SKILLS		1 point	2 points	3 points
Pre-reading	Predicting	The student has great difficulty formulating a prediction.	The student makes predictions about the text but doesn't utilize text clues consistently.	The student utilizes text clues to make logical predictions before, during and after reading.
	Questioning	The student has great difficulty formulating a question for others and relies on teacher support.	The student asks a question that is based on an information of the text.	The student asks a question that requires making inferences about the text.
While-reading	Clarifying	The student is unable to identify anything they find confusing in / about the text.	The student can identify something confusing in/about the text but cannot use a clarifying strategy.	The student can identify something confusing in/about the text and can use a clarifying strategy.
Post-reading	Summarizing	The student has great difficulty summarizing the article	The student summaries most of the article accurately, but has some slight misunderstanding	The student uses only 1-3 sentences to describe clearly that the article is about

The performance of both the control group and the experimental group across the four key reading strate-

gies used in Reciprocal Teaching was shown in the figure 1. The summary for each stage was described as bellowed.

Predicting	Control group					Experimental group					
	T1	T2	T3	T4	Average %	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	Average
	1	1	3	3	66%	3	2	3	3	2	86.6%
Questioning	Control group					Experimental group					
	T1	T2	T3	T4	Average %	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	Average
	2	3	2	3	83.3%	3	2	3	3	3	93.3 %
Clarifying	Control group					Experimental group					
	T1	T2	T3	T4	Average %	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	Average
	2	3	3	1	75 %	3	3	2	3	1	80 %
Summarizing	Control group					Experimental group					
	T1	T2	T3	T4	Average %	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	Average
	3	1	2	2	66.7%	3	3	2	3	2	86.7 %

Figure 1. Progress of the experiment

Predicting: The control group achieved an average of 66%, while the experimental group reached 86.6%. This is a large difference and shows that students in the experimental group became much more effective at making predictions about the text. RTM clearly helped them anticipate content and engage more actively with the reading material.

Questioning: Both groups performed fairly well, but the experimental group still outperformed the control group. The control group scored 83.3%, while the experimental group scored 93.3%. This suggests that Reciprocal Teaching significantly strengthened students' ability to generate meaningful questions and interact with the text at a deeper level.

Clarifying: The clarifying strategy shows the smallest gap between the two groups. The control group averaged 75%, while the experimental group averaged 80%. Although the difference is not as large as in other strategies, the experimental group still shows a

noticeable advantage. This indicates that both groups struggled to some extent with clarifying unclear parts of the text, but RTM still provided an additional boost.

Summarizing: There was strong difference in the summarizing strategy. The control group achieved 66.7%, while the experimental group reached 86.7%. This is a substantial improvement, showing that RTM helped students summarize information more accurately and coherently, reflecting deeper comprehension.

Overall, across all four strategies, the experimental group consistently outperformed the control group. The largest improvements appear in predicting and summarizing, which are higher-order comprehension skills. These results demonstrate that the Reciprocal Teaching Method has a strong positive impact on students' reading strategy use and overall reading comprehension.

Figure 2. Comparative result of Pre-test and post -test scores and RTM

There was a comparison of the average score differences between the control group and the experimental group across three stages: the pre-test, the RTM average, and the post-test. In terms of the key points, first, pre-test score starts at 64% of the control group, which represents their baseline reading comprehension

level before any instruction began. During the instructional period, their average score rises to 72.9%, showing some improvement through regular classroom teaching. However, in the post-test, their score slightly decreases to 68.6%. This tells us that although the students experienced short-term improvement during the

lessons, the traditional method did not support strong long-term retention or consistent progress.

In terms of the experimental group, which was taught using the Reciprocal Teaching Method, their initial pre-test score is already higher, at 78.5% than the control group, but what is important here is the amount of improvement they show. During the RTM sessions, their average score increases significantly to 86.7%. And in the post-test, they reach 87.4%, which indicates not only strong learning during the intervention but also excellent retention of their new skills. When we compare the two groups, the difference becomes very clear. The control group shows a modest gain of about 4.6 percentage points from pre-test to post-test. But the experimental group shows a much larger gain - almost 9 percentage gaps. This demonstrates that the Reciprocal Teaching Method was noticeably more effective in im-

proving students' reading comprehension skills. Overall, the results strongly support the conclusion that RTM leads to better performance, deeper understanding, and stronger long-term learning compared to traditional teaching methods.

In order to provide the research reliability and validity, the semi-structured interviews with 4 questions were undertaken from 20 EFL learners, and they were used to confirm the effectiveness of using reciprocal teaching method in the experimental group. The questions in the table 2 helped us understand both the cognitive and emotional aspects of learning through RTM. Here are some excerpts from student interviews. The following excerpts present students' responses regarding the effects of RTM, their preferences, challenges, and choices when applying the four strategies of predicting, questioning, clarifying, and summarizing the text.

Table 2.

Interview results

1. What were the effects of using reciprocal reading activities in reading comprehension skill?	2. Which strategy did you prefer and why?	3. Which strategy was too difficult for you and why?	4. Would you prefer to use the RTM instead of traditional method of reading? Why?
<i>Although I was not able to speak fluently, it was an effective approach. I enjoyed the discussion and communication with others, which helped me better understand the text and express my opinions. (5 students' responses)</i>	<i>I prefer summarizing, as it allows me to grasp the main idea more easily and improves my summarizing skills. (8 students' responses)</i>	<i>Predicting was the most difficult task for me. (10 students' responses) I found it challenging to make predictions based on only part of the text because they could be incorrect without knowing the whole passage. I also worried that others might not like my prediction.</i>	<i>I prefer the RTM because discussing and collaborating with team members helps me understand the article more easily. It is both fun and effective. (10 students' responses)</i>

Many students preferred summarizing because it helped them grasp the main ideas more easily. Others enjoyed the group discussions and said it helped them understand the text better. One student mentioned struggling with predicting because they felt unsure making assumptions without reading the full text. These responses give us valuable insight into how students perceive the method.

Reciprocal reading activities positively impacted students' reading comprehension skills. They helped identify main ideas, enhanced critical thinking, and made reading more engaging than traditional methods. Working in teams and discussing texts improved communication, problem-solving, and understanding, while also allowing students to fill gaps in their knowledge. The approach further supported vocabulary development, text analysis, and step-by-step reading through prediction, questioning, and clarification.

Students preferred summarizing the most, as it helped them understand the main idea and improve their summarizing skills. Clarifying was also useful for learning unfamiliar phrases and enhancing comprehension through teamwork. Questioning encouraged critical thinking, while prediction made reading more engaging and helped anticipate content.

Among the reciprocal reading strategies, predicting was reported as the most difficult, as it was challenging to make accurate predictions without reading the entire text, and participants worried that others

might disagree with their predictions. Summarizing was also difficult for some students, particularly in expressing ideas clearly in English and writing accurate summaries. Questioning and clarifying posed challenges for a few participants, mainly when explaining unfamiliar content to others. However, some students found the approach overall easy to handle without major difficulties.

Most students preferred using the Reciprocal Teaching Method (RTM) over traditional reading methods. They found that discussing and collaborating with team members made it easier to comprehend texts, enhanced engagement, and improved reading, writing, and speaking skills. Some students also noted that RTM helps develop critical thinking and can be applied for independent learning. A few participants preferred the traditional method or a combination of both approaches, believing that combining methods fosters the growth of skills that are not yet fully developed.

DISCUSSION

Theoretically, John H. Flavell is considered the founder of metacognition research, having introduced and developed the concept extensively through his work. According to him the metacognitive theory explains human mental thinking process (Concept of metacognition). A researcher Mohammad Reza explained reading comprehension strategies that readers use reading comprehension strategies, both cognitive and metacognitive, to better understand reading texts

and in order to learn to read independently in the frame of metacognitive theory (Ahmadi, 2016). The theoretical insights introduced by these scholars provide a basis for interpreting our results as bellowed.

Strategies	Experimental group's average	Control group's average	Interview result	
Predicting	86.6%	66%	Q1	RTM was effective.
Questioning	93.3%	83.3%	Q2	Prefer summarizing even it was difficult.
Clarifying	80%	75%	Q3	Most difficult was prediction
Summarizing	86.7%	66.7%	Q4	Yes

The MRT-based group outperformed the traditionally taught group, indicating that MRT effectively enhances reading comprehension. Consistent with metacognitive theory, this result suggests that learners improve their reading comprehension more effectively when instructional methods encourage them to think actively, monitor their understanding, and use cognitive and metacognitive strategies.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, reciprocal teaching has a significantly positive effect on the English reading comprehension and metacognitive reading strategies of students.

Reciprocal teaching is one of the reading strategy instructions that improve readers' metacognitive awareness. It leads students to think about their reading process, develop a plan of action, monitor their own reading in order to construct their own knowledge, and self-evaluate their reading process.

Reciprocal teaching can help students become more aware of metacognitive strategies through explicit instruction with social interaction, so they can learn gradually and control their own learning process.

Thus, reciprocal teaching should be taken into consideration in order to adapt its implementation in the English reading class.

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